

Sustainable Rural Mechanization Using a Bullock-Powered Rotary System: Performance Evaluation of a Chili Grinding Machine (Mirchi Kandap)

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Abstract:

Bullock-drawn rotary power offers a sustainable energy source for post-harvest operations such as chaff cutting, pulse milling, flour milling, spice grinding, cotton ginning, and briquetting. This study evaluates the performance of a Chili Grinding Machine (Mirchi Kandap) powered by a bullock-operated rotary system.

The draft requirement ranged from 460.6 N to 519.4 N, averaging 493.23 N, which is 5.71% of the paired Red Kandhari bullocks' body weight. Physiological parameters indicated a gradual decrease in pulse rate over time. Mean respiration rates were 26.2 and 28.2 bpm, heart rates 55.2 and 55.2 bpm, and body temperatures 38.17°C and 38.25°C for bullocks B1 and B2, respectively. The bullocks' rpm declined from 58 to 54, while the Chili Grinding Machine shaft maintained a mean speed of 356 rpm.

Machine output decreased slightly with duration, averaging 8.5 kg/h, compared to 10 kg/h under electric motor operation. The system delivered an average power output of 0.522 kW. With a power requirement of 0.5 hp, the unit operated efficiently at a cost of ₹89.36/h, demonstrating the viability of bullock-powered rotary systems for agro-processing in rural settings.

Keywords: Chilly Grinding Machine (Mirchi Kandap), Red Kandhari bullock, draft, pulse rate, rotary mode agro processing unit.

Introduction:

The agro-processing sector currently utilizes approximately 10% of the total draught animal energy available in the country, up from 7% in 1980–81, highlighting a growing reliance on alternative energy sources including mechanical, electrical, and animal power. With current consumption trends, it is projected that liquid fuels and natural gas may be depleted by 2050, and coal reserves by 2250, emphasizing the urgent need to harness renewable and sustainable energy sources, particularly in rural applications.

In the Marathwada region, the average annual utilization of bullock power in agriculture is approximately 500 hours/year in rainfed areas and 900 hours/year in irrigated double-cropping zones—significantly lower than the estimated potential of 2400 hours/year, indicating underutilization of animal energy.

According to the 17th Livestock Census, the state of Maharashtra accounts for 8.8% of the national cattle population. While the population of crossbred cattle increased by 12.9%, the number of indigenous cattle declined by 13.4% between the 16th and 17th censuses, reflecting a shift in breeding patterns that may impact the availability of traditional draught power.

The selection of the proposed research field was guided by these trends, particularly the need for efficient utilization of underused bullock power, the sustainability imperative in rural energy systems, and the regional livestock demographics that support the development of animal-powered agro-processing technologies.

Objectives:

1. To develop an improved bullock-drawn rotary power transmission system.
2. To identify and operate suitable agro-processing units using the developed rotary system.
3. To assess the physiological responses of selected bullock pairs during operation.
4. To evaluate the performance of selected agro-processing machinery powered by animal energy.

The study also aims to estimate the operational cost of bullock utilization at 500 hours/year in

rain fed agriculture and 900 hours/year in irrigated double-crop systems, against the potential of 2400 hours/year. Since bullocks require year-round feeding regardless of usage, underutilization leads to high per-hour operational costs. Increasing annual working hours is essential to reduce the economic burden of ownership. Given the limiting power output of 1 hp per bullock pair, a low-cost, animal-powered rotary system was designed and fabricated to operate small-capacity agro-processing equipment efficiently.

• Experimental Setup

The experimental setup, illustrated in Plate 4.1, consisted of an outdoor circular test track, a pair of test bullocks, a yoke, a rotary power transmission system, an underground shaft, output shafts with V-pulleys, and the selected agro-processing machinery.

• Selection of Animals

A pair of locally bred bullocks aged between 7 and 8 years, with a combined weight of 900 kg, was selected for the experiment. The efficiency and precision of animal-powered operations depend significantly on the animals' training, regular exercise, and proper handling. Initially, the test bullocks were unaccustomed to the rotary motion and exhibited resistance, making handling and operation challenging. However, with time and training, their behavior normalized, and they adapted to the circular motion of the setup.

• Test Track

The test track was a circular plot with a radius of 5.5 meters, developed on a well-compacted and leveled surface, cleared of stones or obstructions. The entire track was elevated by 10 cm above the surrounding ground level to ensure safety and proper drainage. At the center of the track, the gear unit of the power transmission system was mounted on a mild steel (MS) angle frame, firmly anchored in cement concrete using foundation bolts.

• Power Transmission System

The power transmission system was designed to convert animal muscle energy into mechanical energy and consisted of the following major components:

- **Wooden Input Beam:** A hardwood beam of 127.2 mm diameter and 5.0 m length served as the input shaft, transmitting torque generated by the bullocks to the gearbox.

- **Gearbox:** A combination of spur gears, bevel gears, and V-pulleys was employed to amplify the slow rotational speed of the bullocks (~2 rpm) to a usable speed of 1000–1200 rpm, as required by typical low-speed agro-processing machines.

- **Underground Shaft and Output Shaft:** These connected the gearbox to the output V-pulleys and ultimately powered the agro-processing equipment.

Based on literature, the operating speed for small-capacity agro-processing machinery generally ranges from 800 to 1000 rpm. The system was therefore engineered using suitable gear and pulley combinations to achieve the required speed range effectively.

- **Mechanical Components of the Transmission Unit:**

1. Input Shaft
2. Differential Gearbox
3. V-Pulleys
4. Underground Shaft
5. Output Shaft

This configuration ensured efficient transmission of energy from the bullock motion to the processing equipment, making it a viable solution for rural, off-grid agro-processing operations.

- **c) Animal-Driven Rotary Gear Unit**

1. Gearbox Assembly

The gearbox, which houses the transmission components, was fabricated using a 6 mm thick

cast iron plate in a rectangular box shape with dimensions 860 mm × 750 mm × 75 mm.

Plate No.1. Rotary Power Transmission unit

- **Spur Gears:** A set of spur gears was employed to transmit power between two parallel shafts. The gears were made from heat-treated alloy steel, with a module of 3.0 mm. The driving gear had 96 teeth, and the pinion had 23 teeth, resulting in a speed ratio of 1:4.1, thereby achieving a significant speed step-up.

- **Bevel Gears:** A pair of spiral-tooth bevel gears was used to transfer motion at a 90° angle, converting vertical rotation into horizontal. These were also made from heat-treated alloy steel, with a speed ratio of 1:1. The combination of bevel and spur gears provided an effective overall speed multiplication ratio of 1:4.

Plate No. 2. Side View of Power Transmission Unit

2. Shafts

- The first vertical shaft supporting the spur gear had a diameter of 500 mm.

- The second shaft, linked to a 94T spur gear, was coupled to a third shaft with an idler gear (22T) having a diameter of 250 mm, achieving a 1:4 step-up.

- The idler gear (110T) was meshed with a pinion (31T) on the fourth shaft, which was coupled with a belt and pulley system.
- A drive pulley (18") was fixed on the pinion shaft, transmitting power to a 10" pulley attached to the bevel gear, thus converting vertical motion into horizontal motion for the underground shaft of the rotary system.

3. Bearings and Covers

- One ball bearing (90×50×24 mm) was fitted at the bottom of the 50 mm shaft, and another ball bearing (72×30×20 mm) at the top.
- A thrust bearing (60×38×20 mm) was installed at the outer end of the pinion shaft.
- For the underground shaft, four pedestal bearings (300×80×50 mm) were used.
- Bearing covers of various sizes were employed and made from cast iron for durability and protection.
- Belt-Pulley Transmission Unit

The rotary system included two transmission shafts:

- The first (underground) shaft connected directly to the gearbox output. It was extended using a 16-foot coupling shaft for operational reach.
- A 12" pulley mounted on this shaft was linked via a V-belt to a 16" pulley on the countershaft, achieving a speed reduction of 1:0.75.
- For the seed cleaner-cum-grader, an additional step-down was incorporated: from the countershaft (25 cm pulley) to the grader shaft (30 cm pulley), resulting in a speed ratio of 1:0.85.
- The overall speed reduction from input to output shaft of the grader unit was calculated as 1:0.6.
- Yoke and Harnessing System

The harnessing system, essential for effective energy transfer, consisted of a wooden yoke supported on the withers of the bullocks and a strong rope that connected the yoke to the horizontal input beam. This setup ensured efficient transmission of tractive force generated by the animals.

• Measuring Instruments

The following instruments were used for performance evaluation:

1. **Dynamometer:** A digital dynamometer measured the drawbar pull required to rotate the system. The movable yoke allowed total pull to act on the instrument.
2. **Tachometer:** Used to record the rotational speed (RPM) of the output shaft.
3. **Measuring Tape:** Employed for layout and installation measurements.
4. **Vernier Caliper:** Used to measure small components with precision.
5. **Stopwatch:** Utilized to measure bullock walking speed, and for recording pulse and respiration rates, with precision up to 1 microsecond.
6. **Digital Thermometer:** Used to monitor the rectal body temperature of the bullocks.

• Physiological Observations

Physiological parameters were recorded following the method described by Miller and Robertson (1959):

- **Pulse Rate:** Measured by placing a finger on the **coccygeal artery** beneath the tail. Readings were taken at the start and every hour during operation.
- **Respiration Rate:** Determined by counting warm exhalation bursts per minute near the **nostrils**, recorded at the start and hourly thereafter.
- **Body Temperature:** Measured by inserting a clinical thermometer **40–50 mm** into the rectum for **2 minutes**. Temperature readings were recorded at the start and every half hour during testing sessions.

• Work performance:

Draft: Pull is measured with the help of Dynamometer attached between yoke and beam. Draft was calculated from the multiplication of pull into angle made by animal with the direction of travel

$$D = P \times \cos \theta$$

Where,

D = Draft in kgf; P = Pull in kgf

θ = Angle between line of pull and horizontal

Speed: The test bullocks were allowed to travel 5 rotations of the test track.

The time for the same was recorded using a stopwatch.

Speed is calculated with the help of following formula:

$$S = \frac{L}{T} \times 3.6$$

Where,

S = Speed in km/hr;

L = Distance moved or traveled in meter

T = Time required by the bullock to travel certain distance in Second

3.6 = Conversion factor for km/hr

- **Horse power** is the multiplication of draft and speed. Values of the horse power computed as per Broody (1945) from equation,

$$\text{Horse Power (hp)} = \frac{D \times S}{75}$$

Where, D = Draft developed, kg
S = Speed of bullock, m/s

- **Experimental Procedure:**

Experiments were conducted at AICRP on MAH, CAET Parbhani site. The procedure followed is described below:

- **Evaluation of power transmission system:**

The developed power transmission system was evaluated by computing the power, draft and output. The load was applied only after the bullocks attained the desired working speed.

The dynamometer was mounted between yoke and beam, such that the pull exerted by the bullocks was applied to the beam

through the dynamometer and which showed the instantaneous pull acting at the beam. The recorded draught was used to calculate input power.

Test bullocks were hitched and allowed to move on a circular track. The system was tested at no load and loads. The resulted draft was measured using dynamometer. The input power was calculated using the following relations:

$$\text{Input Power (kW)} = \frac{\text{Draft (N)} \times \text{Speed (m/s)}}{1000}$$

- **Physiological Responses of Bullocks:**

The trials were conducted using yoke. Tests were conducted during summer (March-April) season. Trials were conducted using following schedule.

0.5 work + 1h rest + 0.5 work+ 1 h rest
+ 0.5 work

The physiological responses such as respiration rate, pulse rate and body temperature were recorded at the start of work in both the sessions termed as initial values. Then, after every half hour of work the observation were recorded for physiological responses and physical symptoms for both the bullocks separately. The bullock moving in the outer circle was termed as outer bullock and the one moving inside was called inner bullock. The average speed was also calculated.

Plate No. 3. Top View of Rotary Mode Agro –Processing Unit.

• **Performance of selected Agro Processing Unit Chilli Grinding Machine (Mirchi Kandap) :**

For Chili Grinding Machine, Electrical rpm 356 was measured by Tachometer and the Rated rpm with Bullock operating Power Transmission unit rpm 360 was measured. For obtaining same rpm, 25.4 cm pulley to chilly mill shaft 30 cm pulley mounted is in ratio 1:1.18 for minimizing the speed shaft of chilly mill having 7.5 cm pulley to another end of shaft connected to v-belt with pistons of machine pulley 35 cm with the speed ratio 1:0.21 hence the final speed ratio from input to output shaft of chilly mill is 0.18.

Table No.1. Selected Agro-Processing Machine rpm Record

Sr. No.	Machines	Electrical rpm with 1.0 Hp Motor	Rated rpm with Bullock Operating(Power Transmission unit)
1.	Chilly Machine Griding	356	360

Table 2 : Specification of Chilli Grinding Machine (Mirchi Kandap)

Plate No.4. Observations of Chilli Grinding Machine.

Sr. No.	Parameters	Chilly Grinding Machine(Mirchi Kandap)
1.	Length (cm)	125
2.	Width (cm)	50
3.	Height (cm)	107
4.	Weight (kg)	250-265
5.	Number of piston	2
6.	Efficiency (per cent):	85.9-90.3
7.	Power requirement (kw) :	4.3-5.7
8.	Capacity (kg/h) : (depending upon the grain)	8-10

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

• Performance Evaluation of Chilly Griding Machine(Mirchi Kandap) Operation Under No-Load Condition:

The Chilly Griding Machine (Mirchi Kandap) was initially tested under no-load conditions using a pair of Red Kandhari bullocks at the MAH center, to establish baseline parameters for comparison with load condition trials. The summarized data are presented in Table 3.

The initial draft requirement was recorded at 499.8 N, which decreased to 441.0 N after 30 minutes of operation, averaged over three replications. The mean draft was found to be 476.86 N, representing 5.52% of the total body weight of the bullock pair (880 kg).The speed of operation varied between 4.32 km/h and 3.85 km/h across the trials. The mean physiological responses of bullocks B1 and B2 were as follows:

- Respiration Rate: 24.0 and 25.75 breaths per minute (bpm)
- Pulse Rate: 52.75 and 54.0 bpm
- Body Temperature: 37.62°C and 37.92°C

The average power output of the bullocks over the three 30-minute trials was 0.538 kW. The mean shaft speed (RPM) of the chilly mill was observed to be 370 RPM under no-load conditions. The RPM of the bullocks decreased from 63 to 56 over the 30-minute trial duration.

Table.No.3.Performance Evaluation of Chilly Griding Machine (Mirchi Kandap) Operation Under No-Load Condition:

parameters	At no load								mean	
	Duration, h									
	In		0.5		1		1.5		B1	B2
	B1	B2	B1	B2	B1	B2	B1	B2		
Respiration rate, bpm	14	16	24	25	24	27	34	35	24	25.7
pulse rate, bpm	47	48	51	54	55	57	58	57	52.7	54
Body temp, °C	36.9	37.4	37.6	37.8	37.9	38.2	38.1	38.3	37.62	37.92
Fatigue			10	10	13	13	14	14	12	12
Draft, kg	-		51		45		50		48.66	
%body weight	-		5.79		5.11		5.68		5.52	
Draft, N	-		499.8		441		490		476.86	
RPM of bullocks/0.5h	-		63		59		56		59.33	
Speed, m/s	-		1.2		1.13		1.07		1.13	
Speed, km/h	-		4.32		4.06		3.85		4.06	
RPM at m/c shaft	-		370		380		360		370	
RPM at piston	-		86		92		88		86.66	
Power output of Bullock(kW)	-		0.599		0.498		0.524		0.538	
Output(Kg/h)	-		-		-		-		-	

Plate No. 5. Chilly Grinding Machine Observations recorded during no-load condition.

2. Performance Evaluation of Chilly Grinding Machine(Mirchi Kandap) Operation Under Load Condition:

The Chilly Grinding Machine (Mirchi Kandap) was then evaluated under load conditions in rotary mode. The draft requirement ranged from 519.4 N at the start to 460.6 N at the end of the trials. The mean draft was 493.23 N, accounting for 5.71% of the body weight of the bullocks.

As expected, respiration and pulse rates increased with operational duration. The mean physiological responses were recorded as:

- Respiration Rate (B1 and B2): 26.25 and 28.25 bpm
- Pulse Rate (B1 and B2): 55.25 bpm
- Body Temperature: 38.17°C (B1) and 38.25°C (B2), with minimal variation throughout the trial

The RPM of the bullocks gradually declined from 58 to 54, while the mean shaft RPM of the chilly mill under load was 356 RPM. The mean output of the chilly mill was 8.5 kg/h, compared to 10 kg/h when operated with an electric motor. The average power output from the bullocks during load condition trials was 0.522 kW.

These results confirm that Red Kandhari bullocks are capable of performing spice grinding operations efficiently under rotary mode. However, a slight reduction in output and working efficiency was observed, likely due to the non-uniform speed of the bullocks, which affected the consistent up-and-down motion of the screw auger piston. Despite this, the operation was found to be technically feasible considering the draft ability and overall output capacity of the system.

Table.No.4.Performance Evaluation of Chilly Grinding Machine (Mirchi Kandap) Operation Under Load Condition:

parameters	At load								mean	
	Duration, h									
	In		0.5		1		1.5		B1	B2
Respiration rate, bpm	15	17	26	27	28	29	36	40	26.2	28.2
pulse rate, bpm	49	48	52	53	56	58	64	62	55.2	55.2
Body temp, °C	37.8	37.8	38.2	38.3	38.2	38.5	38.5	38.4	38.17	38.25
Fatigue	10	10	14	14	16	16	19	19	16	16
Draft, kg	-		53		47		51		50.33	

%body weight	-	6.02	5.34	5.79	5.71
Draft, N	-	519.4	460.6	499.8	493.23
RPM of bullocks/0.5h	-	58	55	54	55.6
Speed, m/s	-	1.11	1.05	1.03	1.06
Speed, km/h	-	3.99	3.78	3.7	3.81
RPM at m/c shaft	-	350	370	350	356
RPM at piston	-	80	89	82	83
Power output of Bullock(kW)	-	0.576	0.483	0.514	0.522
Output(Kg/h)	-	7.5	8.5	9.5	8.5

Graph No.1. Physiological responses of experimental bullocks in Chilly Griding Machine.

In case of Physiological responses of experimental bullocks in Chilly Griding Machine the increase in respiration rate, pulse rate as usual increased with duration the mean respiration rate, pulse rate of B1 and B2 was observed 26.25 and 28.25 bpm, 55.25 bpm for both b1 and b2 respectively. There was not much variation in the Body temperature of B1 and B2 38.17 and 38.25°C. The rpm of bullocks were 59 to 54 and gradually decreased with duration in three trials of, 30 minutes.

Graph No.2. Evaluation of Rotary Mode Transmission Unit for operating Chilly Griding Machine (Mirchi Kandap).

The mean rpm of the Chilly Griding Machine (Mirchi Kandap) shaft was observed to be 331. The output of machine gradually decreased with

duration may be due to decrease in the speed of shaft of the Chilly Griding Machine (Mirchi Kandap). The mean output was found to be

8.5kg/h were as the output of Chilly Grinding Machine (Mirchi Kandap) operated with electric motor was 10 kg/h. The mean power output from bullock was found to be 0.545 kW. This indicated that the bullock could easily do the spice grinding operation and their utilization could be enhanced. The lower value of working efficiency may be attributed due to minimizing the up-down motion of piston of screw auger by the non uniform speed of bullocks during working of the Chilly Grinding Machine (Mirchi Kandap). The operation of Chilly Grinding Machine (Mirchi Kandap) was found to be feasible considering the draft ability of Red Kandhari bullocks and its output capacity.

Conclusion:

The draft requirement varied in the range 460.6 N to 519.4 N with the mean draft as 493.23 N which was 5.71% of weight of the paired bullocks. The pulse rate as usual decreased with duration the mean respiration rate, for bullock B1 and B2 was 24 and 25.7 5bpm, 56.75 and 55.25 bpm with the body temperature as 38 and 37.9°C at rpm of bullocks were 68 to 62 respectively. The mean rpm of the seed cleaner cum grader shaft was observed to be 320. The mean output 683.3kg/h as with an electric motor was 760 kg/h. The mean power output was 0.545 kW. The operation of seed cleaner cum grader was found to be feasible considering the draft ability of **Red Kandhari** type bullocks. The total cost of operation of unit was calculated Rs. 87.9 / h with an output capacity of grader observed 0.5 hp.

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Conflict of Interest

The authors declared no conflict of interest.

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